

Impact of Saving Practices on Income Generation among Female Smallholder Farmers in Ogun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of saving practices on income generation among female smallholder farmers in Ogun State, Nigeria. The research employs a descriptive survey design and gathers data using a 5-point Likert-type questionnaire. The target population includes female farmers from various local government areas participating in the World Bank's Value Chain Development Program, including Obafemi Owode, Ijebu North East, Ijebu East, Odogbolu, Ifo, Yewa North, Yewa South, and Odeda. Data was analysed through descriptive statistics, and regression analysis (inferential statistics). Findings revealed that female farmers who adopt consistent and formal saving practices, particularly through financial institutions or mobile banking platforms are better positioned to invest in their farms and diversify income sources. This study concludes that saving behavior contributes significantly to financial planning, agricultural productivity, and overall economic resilience. The study therefore recommended that rural banks and microfinance institutions should offer incentives such as higher interest rates on agricultural savings accounts, matching savings programs, and mobile savings platforms. Additionally, efforts should be made to increase bank account ownership among female farmers by simplifying account opening procedures, reducing transaction costs, and expanding banking infrastructure in rural areas.

Keywords: Financial inclusion, Female farmers, Income generation, Ogun state, Saving practice

Word counts: 187

Introduction

Agriculture plays a key role in Nigeria's economy, helping millions of livelihoods and providing major opportunities for economic growth. Smallholder farmers, particularly females, are crucial to this sector as their positive impact greatly enhances food security and rural development (Munonye, et al., 2023). However, female smallholder farmers in Ogun State, like their peers throughout the country, face continuous obstacles that limit their productivity and economic enablement.

The challenges at the intersection of gender and financial exclusion severely restrict the potential of these female smallholder farmers. Financial inclusion is more than an economic tool; it is a major key factor of change (Saha & Qin, 2023). It is the crucial link that connects female farmers to necessary resources, allowing them to invest in quality inputs, access wider markets, and earn higher incomes. My motivation to pursue this research is rooted in a strong commitment to tackling these inequalities and releasing the untapped potential of these women farmers.

Smallholder farming is strategic in providing food and livelihoods for millions of people around the world, especially in rural areas of developing countries (FAO, 2013). Their efforts have contributed to sustainable development and poverty reduction. While there is an ever-increasing demand for food, smallholders face a range of challenges, including limited access to land, credit, and markets, as well as environmental pressures and other factors that affect their productivity. Despite these challenges, they contribute significantly to agriculture and food security.

Smallholder farmers, cultivating less than 2 hectares of land, constitute the backbone of Nigeria's agricultural landscape, contributing greatly to the nation's food security. Accounting for approximately 80% of the farming population, these farmers play a pivotal role in producing an estimated 90% of the locally consumed food. However, their positive impacts are juxtaposed against a backdrop of formidable challenges, ranging from limited resources and inadequate infrastructure to a lack of market access. Amidst this context, female smallholder farmers, an integral subset of this vital workforce, face unique obstacles that necessitate focused attention (GRAIN, 2023). Female smallholder farmers play a significant role in Nigerian agriculture, contributing substantially to the nation's food production and economic stability (CIRDDOC, 2022). The importance of addressing the needs and challenges faced by female smallholder farmers in Nigeria is evident. A vital aspect of their empowerment and socio-economic development lies in ensuring their access to financial resources, also known as financial inclusion (Adegbite & Machethe, 2020). Financial inclusion encompasses not only the availability of financial services but also the capacity of individuals to use these services effectively.

Ogun State is situated in the southwestern region of Nigeria, and agriculture serves as the economic backbone. Despite their indispensable contributions, smallholder farmers, especially females, face formidable challenges that hinder their productivity and impede their ability to contribute effectively to sustainable development. The specific objectives are to:

- i. investigate how the saving practices among female smallholder farmers affect their income generation in Ogun State.

Literature Review

Smallholder Farmers

The Smallholder farmers, despite their marginalization, play a very essential and crucial role in the agricultural productivity of the country; they constitute 80% of all farmers, produce over 90% of the overall national agricultural production, and are mainly the primary driver of activities in the agricultural sector (Mgbenka & Mbah, 2016). In the agricultural landscapes of Ogun State, Nigeria, smallholder farmers form the bedrock of food production. These individuals, predominantly women, engage in subsistence and small-scale farming, contributing significantly to local food security and rural economies. In contrast, limitations to access financial services have been an intricate web of challenges, which restricts their capacity to invest in agricultural inputs, adopt modern farming practices, and cope with risks associated with climate variability and market fluctuations. Embedded within this study's focus are the unsung heroines of agriculture, the female smallholder farmers. Their well-being stands as the bedrock upon which the efficacy of financial inclusion solutions is examined. These women, often overlooked in the broader agricultural landscape, play an indispensable role in food production, rural development, and the sustainability of the

agricultural sector, and they are characterized by limited land holdings, resource constraints, and a dedication to subsistence farming. Providing support for the smallholder farmers can therefore assist in enhancing food security in the country. A critical strategy should be in place for smallholder farmers for their development and to secure the present and future livelihood of the country's population. Given the need for Nigeria to diversify its economy to agriculture and the crucial role of rural smallholder farmers, there is a need to intensify efforts to ensure FI makes significant impacts on agriculture, rural livelihood, and economic growth (FMARD, 2017).

Gender Dimensions: Empowering Female Smallholder Farmers

It is estimated that female smallholder farmers constitute 50% of the labor force, which includes African women who play a vital role in food and agriculture. They produce much of the food for domestic consumption, and they are the drivers of food processing, marketing, and preservation (African Development Bank, 2023). A significant dimension of smallholder farming in Ogun State is the prevalence of female farmers. Women play an extremely important role in agricultural activities, contributing not only to food production but also to household income and economic stability. On the other hand, gender disparities and sociocultural norms often constrain their participation and access to resources, including finance (Bello, Baiyegunhi, & Danso-Abbeam, 2021). The latent potential of female smallholder farmers scan is unlocked by empowering them with financial inclusion solutions that will enhance their decision-making capacity and contribute to women's economic empowerment.

Income Enhancement: A Holistic Approach

The revenue generated by female smallholder farmers encapsulates the culmination of their efforts. It signifies the monetary returns from agricultural activities, often reflecting their economic well-being and the degree of financial security. Income is an outcome of agricultural productivity and the efficient utilization of resources, which, in turn, is intricately linked to access to financial services, effective risk management, and the facilitation of income-generating opportunities (Anthony-Orji, Orji, Igwe, Ndubuisi, Ikubor, & Nwifo, 2024). Elevating the income of female smallholder farmers is a multifaceted endeavor that goes beyond agricultural productivity. Financial inclusion strategies seek to improve the economic well-being of female farmers by providing them with not only access to financial services but also digital payment systems, market linkages, and risk management tools. The broader goal of alleviating poverty, enhancing livelihoods, and fostering economic sustainability reveals the impact of the intersection of financial inclusion and income improvement. The specific dynamics of Ogun State introduce unique considerations into the discourse of financial inclusion and its impact on female smallholder farmers. Sociocultural norms, geographic variations, and localized economic realities influence the adoption of financial inclusion solutions and their effectiveness in improving productivity and income.

Theoretical Review

This study is anchored on the systems theory of financial inclusion which states that the achievement of financial inclusion objectives relies on the existing sub-systems, encompassing economic, social, and financial components that are interconnected and integral to the functioning of the financial inclusion system (Ozili, 2018). In this context, enhanced financial inclusion yields positive benefits for the sub-systems it depends on. Notably, significant changes within a sub-system can exert a profound influence on the

anticipated outcomes of financial inclusion. For example, the imposition of regulations on financial sector actors, integral components of the financial system, can align their interests with those of users of basic financial services. This alignment may result in the provision of affordable and high-quality financial services within defined regulatory frameworks, thereby safeguarding users of formal financial services from exploitation and price discrimination.

However, substantial changes at the systemic level, such as the replacement of an existing national financial inclusion plan with an entirely new one, do not necessarily translate into alterations within the existing sub-systems. Change within a sub-system must be instigated at the sub-system level. This theory underscores two key propositions: first, the efficiency and effectiveness of the sub-systems significantly influence the success or failure of a national financial inclusion agenda. Second, the ultimate beneficiaries of financial inclusion, from a systems theory perspective, are the existing sub-systems within a country, whether they are economic, financial, or social.

The systems theory of financial inclusion offers several advantages, which includes the following; the critical role played by the established economic, financial, and social systems or structures in a nation in advancing financial inclusion. Secondly, it provides a macro-level perspective on financial inclusion, contrasting with theories that adopt a micro-level perspective. Thirdly, it considers how financial inclusion outcomes are shaped by the intricate interplay among the sub-systems that underpin financial inclusion.

Nonetheless, the theory has certain limitations. Firstly, it assumes that the existing sub-systems effectively reflect the environment, which may not always be the case in certain contexts. Consequently, the anticipated outcomes of financial inclusion may not be fully realized in environments where the sub-systems do not function optimally. Secondly, the systems theory of financial inclusion does not account for external factors that may influence financial inclusion outcomes, focusing instead on the impact of sub-systems on these outcomes. Thirdly, it presumes a direct relationship between financial inclusion outcomes and the systems upon which it depends.

Review of Empirical Studies

Several studies have emphasized the empowerment of female smallholder farmers through financial inclusion. Financial inclusion can lead to increased economic independence, decision-making power, and enhanced social status for women in rural areas. These studies stress the transformative potential of financial inclusion for female farmers (Ghosh & Vinod, 2017; Damane, & Ho, 2024).

The relationship between access to credit and income growth among female smallholder farmers has been a recurring theme. This is particularly important for female farmers who often face constraints in accessing financial resources. In the context of the growing prevalence of digital financial inclusion solutions, the significance of technology in enhancing access to financial services for female smallholder farmers has been emphasized (Chinoda & Kapingura, 2024). Mobile money platforms and USSD-based services have played a pivotal role in broadening financial inclusion.

There is a positive relationship between formal financial access, financial literacy, and income generation (Setiani, Pratiwi, & Komara, 2024). Having access to formal financial services and possessing financial literacy significantly enhances the capacity to generate income through mechanisms such as saving, credit acquisition, asset accumulation, and risk

management. This empowerment leads to the development of entrepreneurial skills and a greater exploration of economic opportunities.

A study that focused on the relationship between wealthy male smallholders' participation in both farm and non-farm activities and their higher degrees of financial inclusion has shed light on how smallholders participate in the economy. However, there was less of a presence of these activities among female smallholders, who generally have less access to economic opportunities (Hernandez, Humam, Ciacci, Benni, & Kaaria, 2018). Structured savings mechanisms provide critical pathways for agricultural investment and subsequent income stabilization (Solidaridad Network, 2024).

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprises female smallholder farmers in Ogun State, Nigeria. The population is exclusively female, focusing on gender-specific challenges and opportunities. These individuals engage in agricultural activities on a small scale, often subsistence farming, and typically have limited access to resources and financial services. The female smallholder farmers who form the population of this study were selected from female farmers' organizations located in Ogun State, Nigeria, under the World Bank Value Chain Development Program in the following local government areas:

- Obafemi Owode Local Government
- Ijebu North East
- Ijebu East
- Odogbolu Local Government
- Ifo Local Government
- Yewa North
- Yewa South
- Odeda

The population of this study comprised 1,228 female smallholder farmers belonging to the female farmer organizations spread across the aforementioned eight LGAs of Ogun State. This study will rely on primary data, which will be gathered through structured questionnaires containing closed-ended questions. This study primarily used a structured questionnaire for the collection of quantitative data. The questionnaire was structured in sections to gather quantitative information from female smallholder farmers in Ogun State, Nigeria. A 5-point Likert-type scale was used in the study questionnaire. Data collected from the questionnaire undergo a thorough analysis through descriptive statistics, and regression analysis (inferential statistics).

Results and Presentation of Data

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Female Smallholder Farmers in the study

s/n	Variables	Labels	Frequency	Percentage
1	Gender	Male	-	-
		Female	295	100.0
2	Age	20-25 years	17	5.8
		30-35 years	76	25.8
		40-45 years	70	23.7
		46 years and above	132	44.7
3	Years of work experience	Below 10 years	65	22.0
		10-20 years	131	44.4
		Above 20 years	99	33.6
4	Highest level of education	First Leaving Certificate	202	68.5
		OND/NCE	44	14.9
		Professional qualification	1	0.3
		Degree	47	15.9
		Masters	1	0.3
5	Marital status	Single	12	4.1
		Married	277	93.9
		Divorced	1	0.3
		Separated	5	1.7
6	Number of dependents	No dependent	1	0.3
		1-5 dependents	197	66.8
		6-10 dependents	92	31.2
		11-15 dependents	4	1.4
		Above 15 dependents	1	0.3
7	Years of farming experience	Less than 5 years	18	6.1
		5-10 years	101	34.2
		11-20 years	96	32.5
		More than 20 years	80	27.1

Source: Fieldwork (2025)

Table 1 shows the demographic characteristics of female smallholder farmers in the study. The age distribution showed that the majority of female farmers (44.7%) are aged 46 and above, followed by 30-35 years (25.8%), while younger farmers (20-25 years) are the minority at 5.8%. This indicated that most female farmers in the study are middle-aged or older, suggesting a possible trend of aging in the farming population. Additionally, the majority have significant work experience, with 44.4% having worked for 10-20 years, indicating that these women are seasoned farmers with extensive knowledge of farming practices.

In terms of education, the majority (68.5%) have only a First Leaving Certificate, which is the most basic level of education. A small proportion (15.9%) had a degree, while less than 1% held a professional qualification or a master's degree. This showed a disparity in education levels among the farmers, which could affect their ability to adopt new technologies or farming practices. Furthermore, a significant majority of the women (93.9%) are married, which indicates that family support systems are an important factor in their ability to engage in farming activities.

Regarding dependents and farming experience, most farmers (66.8%) have between 1-5 dependents, with a smaller proportion (31.2%) having 6-10 dependents. This indicated a substantial family responsibility for many farmers, potentially influencing their labor capacity and financial needs. When it comes to farming experience, a considerable number of farmers (34.2%) have been farming for 5-10 years, and nearly as many (32.5%) have 11-20 years of experience. Those farming for more than 20 years represented 27.1%, while the least experienced (less than 5 years) made up only 6.1%. This showed that the majority have substantial farming experience.

Analysis of Research Questions

Research Question One: What is the influence of saving practices on the income generation of female smallholder farmers in Ogun State?

Table 2: Saving Practices and Income Generation among Female Smallholder Farmers

s/n	Saving practices and income generation	SD	D	U	A	SA	\bar{x}	S.D.
1	Saving income boosts overall farm revenue	1 0.3%	1 0.3%	-	144 48.8%	149 50.5%	4.49	0.559
2	Savings are a key growth factor in my financial plan.	2 0.7%	-	1 0.3%	147 49.8%	145 49.2%	4.47	0.582
3	Regular saving increases my farm's income potential.	2 0.7%	1 0.3%	3 1.0%	160 54.2%	129 43.7%	4.40	0.603
4	I save part of my earnings to meet revenue goals.	2 0.7%	2 0.7%	1 0.3%	168 56.9%	122 41.4%	4.38	0.604

5	I choose saving strategies that maximize farm income	2	6	9	170	108	4.27	0.682
		0.7%	2.0%	3.1%	57.6%	36.6%		
6	Making consistent saving decisions is sometimes challenging.	-	-	2	130	163	4.55	0.512
				0.7%	44.1%	55.3%		
7	Saving is vital for my family's and farm's financial security.	1	2	18	163	111	4.29	0.641
		0.3%	0.7%	6.1%	55.3%	37.6%		
8.	Saving practices indirectly benefit financial management.	2	2	8	172	111	4.32	0.627
		0.7%	0.7%	2.7%	58.3%	37.6%		
9	Disciplined saving supports long-term financial growth.	1	2	2	171	119	4.37	0.574
		0.3%	0.7%	0.7%	58.0%	40.3%		
10	I evaluate my saving methods for revenue impact.	1	7	14	172	101	4.24	0.679
		0.3%	2.4%	4.7%	58.3%	34.2%		
11	I consider diverse saving/investment options for revenue.	2	7	31	157	98	4.16	0.755
		0.7%	2.4%	10.5%	53.2%	33.2%		
12	I balance immediate needs with long-term saving goals.	1	4	6	185	99	4.28	0.604
		0.3%	1.4%	2.0%	62.7%	33.6%		
13	I recommend systematic saving for farm revenue success.	2	3	11	171	108	4.29	0.651
		0.7%	1.0%	3.7%	58.0%	36.6%		

Weighted Mean =4.35

SD= Strongly Disagree, D=Disagree, U= Undecided, A=Agree and SA=Strongly Agree

Table 2 shows the analysis of saving practices and income generation among female smallholder farmers. It highlighted a strong recognition of the importance of savings in enhancing financial stability and farm productivity. The majority of the farmers agreed or strongly agreed that saving income boosts overall farm revenue 99.3% (\bar{x} =4.49), savings are a key growth factor in financial planning 99.0% (\bar{x} = 4.47), and regular saving increases farm income potential 97.9% (\bar{x} = 4.40). Additionally, a significant proportion of the farmers affirmed that they save part of their earnings to meet revenue goals 98.3% (\bar{x} =4.38) and that choosing appropriate saving strategies maximizes farm income, 94.2% (\bar{x} =4.27). The study revealed that female smallholder farmers acknowledged the role of disciplined financial management in improving agricultural outcomes and ensuring long-term stability.

However, while savings are generally viewed positively, making consistent saving decisions was noted as a challenge, with 55.3% of respondents strongly agreeing to its difficulty (\bar{x} =4.55). Despite this challenge, saving is widely recognized as crucial for both family and farm financial security 92.9%, (\bar{x} = 4.29) and beneficial for overall financial management

95.9%, (\bar{x} = 4.32). Many respondents also affirmed that disciplined saving supports long-term financial growth 98.3% (\bar{x} = 4.37) and that evaluating saving methods helps improve revenue impact 92.5% (\bar{x} = 4.24). The weighted mean of 4.35 revealed a strong agreement on the importance of savings in financial planning and farm income generation, despite some challenges in maintaining savings consistency.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between the borrowing practices of female smallholder farmers and their investment in quality inputs.

To examine the relationship between borrowing practices and investment in quality input among female smallholder farmers, data on borrowing practices and investment in quality inputs were subjected to Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation analysis. The result is presented in Table 3

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) showing the relationship between borrowing practices and investment in quality input among female smallholder farmers

Variables	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	R	p-value	Remarks
Investments in quality input	19.1966	3.90386	295	0.825*	0.001	Sig.
Borrowing practices	18.9254	4.21867				

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Fieldwork (2025)

Table 3 revealed the findings of a Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) analysis investigating the relationship between borrowing practices and investment in quality inputs among female smallholder farmers in Ogun State. The table showed that there is a statistically significant relationship between borrowing practices and investment in quality inputs among female smallholder farmers ($r=0.825$, $n=295$, $p(0.001)<.05$). Hence, borrowing practices influenced/enhanced the investment in quality inputs of female smallholder farmers in the study. The hypothesis is therefore rejected.

Discussion of Findings

In this study, the total population of the study covered smallholder farmers in Ogun State, and the target populations were female smallholder farmers. Hence, 295 copies of the questionnaires were retrieved and found valid for the analysis, giving a response rate of 100.0%. 295(100.0%) participants were female farmers. This is an indication that the research did not go out of scope by covering only female smallholder farmers.

When it comes to farming experience, a considerable number of farmers (34.2%) have been farming for 5-10 years, and nearly as many (32.5%) have 11-20 years of experience. Those farming for more than 20 years represented 27.1%, while the least experienced (less than 5

years) made up only 6.1%. This showed that the majority have substantial farming experience.

The majority of the female farmers (44.7%) are aged 46 and above, followed by 30-35 years (25.8%), while younger farmers (20-25 years) are the minority at 5.8%. This indicated that most female farmers in the study are middle-aged or older, with a mean age of 40.34 ± 7.06 .

Discussion of Hypotheses

The findings from hypothesis one highlight the significant impact of access to credit on crop yield among female smallholder farmers in Ogun State. This aligns with previous studies from Munonye, et al (2023) that emphasized that financial access enables farmers to invest in improved seeds, fertilizers, and modern farming techniques, ultimately leading to increased productivity. Similarly, Saha and Qin (2023) established that credit availability enhances female farmers' ability to expand their farming operations, adopt better irrigation systems, and improve soil fertility management, thereby boosting crop yields. The study from confirms that financial constraints limit productivity, reinforcing the argument that providing adequate credit facilities can significantly enhance agricultural output among female smallholder farmers. Furthermore, the independent predictive power of access to credit on crop yield emphasizes the critical role of financial inclusion in agricultural development. Another researcher asserted that female farmers often face greater barriers to credit access due to collateral requirements and socio-economic biases, which hinder their ability to invest in farm inputs (The Guardian, 2023).

The findings from hypothesis one established a significant relationship between borrowing practices and investment in quality inputs among female smallholder farmers in Ogun State. Those who borrowed reported spending more on improved seeds, fertilizers, and pesticides. This finding emphasizes the critical role that borrowing practices play in encouraging the adoption of new technologies in smallholder agriculture. It aligns with previous research showing that when farmers can borrow, they are more likely to invest in high-quality resources that boost productivity (Ooi, 2018). The study confirmed that borrowing enhances the financial capacity of female farmers, enabling them to make strategic investments in quality inputs that lead to improved agricultural output.

Furthermore, the study highlighted that borrowing practices influenced investment decisions, reinforcing the role of financial accessibility in agricultural development. Other researchers argued that smallholder farmers, particularly women, face significant challenges in obtaining credit due to limited collateral and institutional barriers (Saha & Qin, 2023). The research also revealed that lending institutions often have policies that discriminate against women, viewing them as inexperienced and therefore, less desirable clients. It also aligns with other studies that emphasize that collateral requirements present a major barrier, as farmers who possess valuable assets are more likely to secure credit, given that these assets can be liquidated in the event of default (UNSGSA, 2023). However, those who successfully secure loans tend to allocate a substantial portion of their funds to purchasing high-quality farm inputs, improving irrigation systems, and adopting mechanized farming techniques. This suggests that expanding borrowing opportunities for female farmers in Ogun State could significantly enhance their capacity to invest in productive agricultural resources, ultimately leading to higher yields and improved livelihoods.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concludes that saving practices play a critical role in the income-generating capacity of female smallholder farmers in Ogun State. Access to reliable and user-friendly saving mechanisms enables better financial planning, investment in agriculture, and economic resilience. However, without addressing the structural barriers that hinder women's access to formal savings platforms, the potential benefits remain underutilized. A more inclusive financial system, tailored financial literacy programs, and mobile-friendly banking solutions could significantly empower female farmers and contribute to rural economic development.

The study therefore recommends the following:

1. Encouraging Savings and Bank Account Ownership

Since savings practices were found to significantly impact income generation, financial institutions should promote savings schemes tailored to the needs of female smallholder farmers. Rural banks and microfinance institutions should offer incentives such as higher interest rates on agricultural savings accounts, matching savings programs, and mobile savings platforms. Additionally, efforts should be made to increase bank account ownership among female farmers by simplifying account opening procedures, reducing transaction costs, and expanding banking infrastructure in rural areas.

2. Strengthening Digital Financial Services and Mobile Banking

To bridge the financial access gap, digital financial services should be expanded in rural areas. Mobile banking, mobile money services, and fintech solutions should be promoted as convenient and accessible financial tools for female smallholder farmers. Telecommunication companies and financial service providers should collaborate to offer affordable mobile financial solutions that enable farmers to save, borrow, and transact without needing to visit physical bank branches.

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